

IMPACT OF THE AGE IN THE LANGUAGE LEARNING PROCESS

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Abstract: In this article, modern methods of teaching foreign languages are analyzed in terms of their importance as well as the modern teaching methods necessary for their study. In addition, the importance of age in language teaching, the difference between older and younger language learners, and how to teach a language to a young person were considered.

Keywords: foreign language, methodology, age, learners, teaching language.

Teaching a foreign language to people of all ages is important at the current stage of society's development. The effectiveness of such education in international communications in various fields is that it ensures the development of relations between people and countries, increases the professional competence of a person, and appears as a new stage of personal development.

Although early learners are more likely than adults to achieve better results in second language settings, it cannot be ruled out that some gifted adults will eventually achieve second language proficiency equivalent to first language proficiency. According to literature reviews, most adults are vocal. Syntax literature reviews show that vocabulary and overall language skills are well acquired by adult learners. Nevertheless, because there are successful cases of adult learners, the long-term benefits of second language learning for most early learners cannot be denied. In general, early learners in second language learning have a clearer advantage in eventual success. However, the advantage of early learners in a non-native language environment over a second language environment is not very clear. The literature has shown that there are large differences between foreign and second language environments:

- quality and quantity of language input; Lessons are limited to 2-4 times a week for around 50 minutes.
- the objectives of language teaching; The target language is not a peer-to-peer communication language and should not be used outside of the classroom.
- Language skills of teachers; The teacher's oral skills may be limited in the target language. Therefore, the corresponding studies in the foreign language environment show that under the same educational conditions, the language level of early language learners is not necessarily better than that of late language learners¹

Literature shows that there are many reasons for the contradictory results of the study on the age effect in the second language, and one of the main reasons is the different study methods used in these studies. In terms of the type of study, Linguistic and psychological

¹ Liang Xu .The Age Effect in Second Language Acquisition and Its Study Design Method. Journal of Education, Humanities and Social Sciences.2023.

study methods such as behavioral study and neurological study, longitudinal study and cross-sectional study, qualitative study, and quantitative study have been widely used in the exploration of the age effect in second language acquisition. When it comes to a specific study on the age effect, there are great differences in the selection of subjects, the determination of investigation content, and the determination of comparison time.

Most psychologists believe that a person's memory becomes more logical than mechanical as they age; they note that their memory is getting stronger but their short-term memory is getting weaker. Also, they prove from the development of logical thinking, accumulated experience, and acquired knowledge that drawing conclusions helps fill the volume of short-term memory. Therefore, the majority of adult learners are mostly younger students, which differs in the following aspects:

1. An adult learner is independent, self-directed, has a rich life, and believes that he has educational experience.
2. An adult learner has a clear motivation for education. It can be seen in training because he is a professional and, with the help of educational activities, believes that he will be able to solve his problems.
3. The knowledge and skills acquired by an adult learner in everyday life seek immediate practical application in professional activities.
4. An adult learner expects high quality and results from the educational process, which sometimes requires

Foreign language learners of different ages have different learning environments. Intelligence level There are many difficulties in experimental studies on this point, and due to the variety of maturity levels and metrics, it is difficult to draw satisfactory conclusions. Different criteria for subject selection: Due to different study subjects and different comparison periods, there are unavoidable differences between studies on the effects of age on second language acquisition for validation or imitation. As a reader, there is no way to determine which study results are more objective and reliable. Therefore, there is a need to further investigate and improve the design of age effect study methods to avoid the shortcomings of previous study methods.

When comparing younger and older learners, the effect of learning a new language by senior language learners is as follows increases due to factors:

increase of internal motivation towards language education;
high assessment of one's ability and potential in the process of language learning;
to reveal one's own internal capabilities in overcoming psychological obstacles, development, forecasting, and design.

The cognitive-communicative method in language teaching to adults, i.e., knowing the language system and teaching through awareness and understanding, pays off. At the same time, imitation and reproduction methods give positive results only in the early stages of education. In this regard, it is appropriate to use methods based on a person-oriented approach².

Co-teaching them, the project method, the "learner's portfolio", internet technologies, and many other technologies can be cited as examples. As mentioned above, as adult learners

² G. Asilova. Andragogical features of teaching Uzbek as a foreign language in an adult audience. Conference paper, December 2021

learn a new language, their motivation will be strong in terms of professional growth. However, in the mother tongue, especially in the professional field, a lack of vocabulary creates difficulties in learning a new language. Linguistic experience gained during the practice of one foreign language in another foreign language has proven to help with successful learning. The result of learning a foreign language is a psychologically and emotionally favorable situation for a person, and it will depend on the character of the interaction between the subjects of education. And this is important in the formation of a group of young people; not only the level of language knowledge but also the age of the group members also requires consideration.

In addition, some studies have shown that adult learners are more efficient than younger learners. Based on these studies, adult learners can use their metalinguistic knowledge, memory strategies, and problem-solving skills; therefore, they could be better at second or foreign language instruction. In educational settings, learners who begin learning a second language at the primary school level do not always achieve greater proficiency in the long run than those who begin in adolescence. Moreover, there are so many adult learners who can achieve excellence in a second or foreign language.

Furthermore, based on my observation in the English course, the age factor does not have any effect on the learners success in acquiring the language. There was an adult who took an English course. He wanted to learn English because he was in touch with the foreigners at his workplace. So, it forced him to learn English, and he could do better than the others. While all the learners in that English course class were around twelve to fifteen years old, even though at first the adult learner had some difficulties with grammar and pronunciation, he could handle it. This is due to the fact that motivation can be more important than age. Many learners have different reasons for coming to the English class³.

Another important aspect of language education is the language itself, which is divided into groups according to the level of knowledge. This is also important in adult education. This ensures that a listener will strive for a higher level of education. If this aspect is not taken into account, it will have a negative impact not only on the effectiveness of education but also on motivation. Today, in contrast to traditional language education, learning material is verbatim; no understanding is required. It is necessary to pay attention to this, especially in the education of all ages. In mastering and strengthening the material, focus on understanding the material, not on memory.

Thus, only learners who have the willingness to learn and want to master the target language will be successful learners. In addition, people who want to study abroad have to learn the target language in order to pass the admission test. This is because they have strong motivation to go abroad. It is called instrumental motivation. It will be a great effect to learn the language and be a successful learner. No matter how old he or she is, motivation is the key to acquiring the language.

To my way of thinking, teachers should be showing the ability to create interesting new things by using new and interesting media. Attractive media can increase learners' involvement in the process of teaching and learning. Media that can be classified into four types. (They are visual and sound and combine video, words, and pictures together.) The most interesting

³ Sakhi Herwiana. The effect of age in english language teaching: is it true?. Article in lingua scientia jurnal bahasa · november 2017

media is because it has sound and colorful, moving pictures, like a movie. To make this kind of medium, we have to use high technology. Therefore, the teachers should have the ability to use technology in order to create an attractive medium. However, in time and history, there have been so many interesting media available in the store. We do not have to be busy to create and make media.

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